

Planning and Inverse Kinematics of Hyper-Redundant Manipulators with VO-FABRIK

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Abstract—Hyper-redundant Robotic Manipulators (HRMs) offer great dexterity and flexibility of operation, but solving Inverse Kinematics (IK) is challenging. In this work, we introduce VO-FABRIK, an algorithm combining Forward and Backward Reaching Inverse Kinematics (FABRIK) for repeatable deterministic IK computation, and an approach inspired from velocity obstacles to cope with self and external collisions. We show preliminary results on a HRM for inspection of industrial plants and hazardous scenarios. Our algorithm achieves good performance where other state-of-the-art IK algorithms fail.

Index Terms—Inverse Kinematics, Robot Planning, Obstacle Avoidance, Hyper-Redundant Manipulators, Velocity Obstacles

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyper-redundant Robotic Manipulators (HRMs) guarantee high dexterity and are particularly suitable for operation in highly constrained environments, e.g., aerospace, search-and-rescue, and complex system maintainance [1]. However, planning and control of HRMs in Cartesian space becomes extremely challenging as the number of Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) increases. In fact, Inverse Kinematics (IK) cannot be solved in closed form, but task-specific criteria must be defined to optimize joint configuration, satisfying constraints as joint limits, obstacle avoidance, and self-collisions.

Recent algorithms are based on geometric resolution of the redundancy [2] or machine learning methods [3]. Typically, the latter requires high learning time and does not guarantee repeatability for reliable operation in hazardous environments and in the presence of human operators. Geometric approaches are repeatable and efficient, but are often very task-specific.

In this abstract, we introduce VO-FABRIK, an algorithm combining motion planning with Velocity Obstacles (VO) [4] and collision-free IK of HRMs. The basis of our methodology is Forward and Backward Reaching Inverse Kinematics (FABRIK) [5], an iterative methodology developed originally for IK in animations. Existing FABRIK applications to robotic manipulation consider few DoFs [6] or do not guarantee joint limit and collision avoidance [7]. Instead, we extend FABRIK with collision cones inspired from VO, to ensure goal reaching and constraint satisfaction.

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We test VO-FABRIK on a simulated HRM with 19 rotational DoFs, in the task of entering and exploring narrow spaces. We also compare it with the performance of BioIK [8], a state-of-the-art generic IK solver based on evolutionary algorithms.

II. VO-FABRIK

We now introduce the basics of FABRIK and collision cones from VO, before showing how they are integrated in VO-FABRIK.

A. Velocity Obstacles (VO)

The VO algorithm for dynamic motion planning computes the set of admissible velocities \mathcal{V}_a for a robot R , given a target G and N obstacles defined by their radius (assuming a spherical shape for simplicity), current position and relative velocity to R . At a given time step, the robot would reach its target with a velocity v_{pref} directed from R to G . To avoid collisions, for each i -th obstacle a *collision cone* CC_i is computed as the set of robot velocities which will cause collision with i -th obstacle. Admissible velocities are then in the range $\mathcal{V}_a = \mathcal{V} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^N CC_i$, where \mathcal{V} is the full velocity space for the robot. If $v_{pref} \notin \mathcal{V}_a$, another velocity must be executed according to a heuristic, e.g., $v \in \mathcal{V}_a$ which has shortest Euclidean distance from v_{pref} .

B. FABRIK

FABRIK algorithm solves the IK for a N -link geometry iteratively, performing backward and forward steps. It starts from the goal end-effector position $p_G = (x_G, y_G, z_G)$ at timestamp t_k , and the positions $p_i, \forall i = 0 \dots N$ of link extrema (p_0 being the base of the robot). In the backward step (Figure 1a), p_N is set to p_G . Then, a segment from p_N to p_{N-1} is built, with the same length as N -th link. Its extremal point represents the new position p_{N-1} at t_{k+1} . The procedure is repeated for all links up to the base. Then, in the forward step, the revers algorithm is applied, setting the newly computed p_0 to the original one (the base must remain fixed). Forward and backward steps are executed until $\|p_N - p_G\|_2 < \epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$. In this way, FABRIK computes the joint configuration solving the IK problem with minimal displacement from the original configuration. It is important to mention that no collision avoidance is considered at this stage.

Fig. 1: a) FABRIK backward iteration from black to red configuration; b) VO-FABRIK avoiding collision for link i , commanding blue configuration instead of red, avoiding the blue collision cone (obstacle) within the green cone (joint limits); c) the simulated task with the Float Arm.

C. VO-FABRIK

Given a target G to be reached by the robot, in the *motion planning phase* the velocity of the end effector is set to v_{pref} in the direction of G , with arbitrary module, resulting in a displacement from p_N to p'_N within a predefined time step t_s . The module of v_{pref} and t_s can be tuned to guarantee finer collision avoidance and navigation in tiny or cluttered spaces.

Then, in the *IK phase*, FABRIK starts with the backward step for each i -th link (a 2D example is shown in Figure 1b) However, within t_s this may result either in a collision with obstacles or other links, or in exceeding the joint limits (red in figure). Hence, we build a cone with vertex at p_{i-1} embedding each obstacle / other link¹ (blue). We also build a (green) cone to encompass joint limits. Our algorithm then assigns the new position p_i in order to preserve motion feasibility. Cones delimit the safe rotation for i -th link, hence they define the space of safe angular velocities, resembling *CCs*. Differently from [7], constraints are considered *jointly and not sequentially*, guaranteeing their satisfaction. In 3D space, links and obstacles can be projected to orthogonal planes in robot base frame, where the 2D algorithm is then applied.

III. RESULTS

We test VO-FABRIK in a simulated environment with the Float Arm, shown in Figure 1c. Float Arm is hibot's snake manipulator that can navigate in complex environments and acquire detailed data for inspection and maintenance. In this scenario, Float Arm enters through a narrow opening and explore a cavity up and down. The trajectory is calculated using a time step of $t_s = 0.02$ s. Starting from home configuration shown in figure, BioIK² with an external VO-based planner is not able to find a configuration for solving the

¹For any other link $j \neq i$, it is possible to compute p^* as the closest point on link j with respect to i , and build a spherical obstacle with link dimensions around p^* .

²For a fair comparison with FABRIK, we set BioIK optimization goal to minimize joint displacement.

task without self-collisions. On the contrary, VO-FABRIK succeeds, achieving on average low computational time per step (0.017 s) and small joint displacement (0.053 rad). We also modify the home configuration of the robot, unwrapping links to avoid self-collisions. However, BioIK can only slightly enter the cavity, achieving small joint displacement (0.001 rad) but requiring 1.96 s per step.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

We presented VO-FABRIK, an algorithm combining FABRIK and VO for motion planning and collision-free IK within joint limits. Our methodology is particularly suited for HRMs, can deal with both spherical and rotational joints and outperforms state-of-the-art BioIK algorithm. In the future, we will further assess the performance of our algorithm with multiple scenarios and robots. Moreover, we will extend the capabilities of our algorithm to also consider the orientation in goal configuration, currently not supported from FABRIK.

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